

Original Article

Ownership Structure and Firm Performance Dynamics in Emerging Markets

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Abstract

The main aim of this research is to explore how ownership concentration influences the performance of firms across different countries and market scales, including large, medium, and small-cap companies in selected emerging economies. The study utilizes a dataset with 3,394 annual observations from 232 publicly traded firms in these economies, spanning from 2004 to 2018. Panel data models and two-step GMM estimation are employed to address potential endogeneity issues. The results indicate that concentrated ownership improves firm oversight, reduces agency conflicts, and enhances profitability. Furthermore, the study reveals varying impacts across different market capitalizations, with liquidity emerging as a key factor for smaller firms. These findings highlight the need for customized corporate governance and financial management strategies to boost firm performance in emerging markets, while also reflecting the ongoing influence of historical performance on current financial results.

Keywords: Corporate governance, Emerging economies, Firms' performance, Ownership concentration

1. INTRODUCTION

Ownership concentration plays a critical role in shaping financial performance and corporate governance, with varying impacts based on the extent of concentration. Higher levels of ownership concentration can potentially improve decision-making and responsiveness within firms. This study explores how ownership concentration affects firm performance, optimal ownership structures, and related regulatory issues. While dispersed ownership can empower minority shareholders, excessive concentration might stifle innovation, especially in sectors that rely heavily on knowledge and creativity. The effects of ownership concentration across different market capitalizations—large, medium, and small-cap—require further exploration.

Current equity markets reveal a trend towards concentrated ownership in publicly traded companies, alongside diverse global ownership structures. Historically, corporate governance discussions have concentrated on dispersed ownership, highlighting the challenge of aligning managerial and shareholder interests. The “separation of ownership and control,” as identified by Berle and Means (1932), remains a fundamental concern in corporate governance. In firms with widely dispersed shareholders, managerial decisions often lack direct oversight, leading to the “agency problem,” where managers may prioritize personal interests over those of shareholders.

Ownership concentration is viewed as a vital corporate governance strategy due to the significant influence exerted by major

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shareholders on company operations and decisions (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Nguyen, Locke, & Reddy, 2015; Shleifer & Vishny, 1986). The ongoing debate among scholars concerns whether concentrated or dispersed ownership structures are more effective for business performance. While a well-structured ownership model can mitigate agency conflicts and enhance performance, it can also lead to increased agency costs and reduced firm value (Balsmeier & Czarnitzki, 2017).

This study investigates the relationship between ownership concentration and firm performance in emerging economies, providing fresh and comprehensive insights. It first examines how ownership concentration influences the performance of listed firms in these economies. Subsequently, it analyzes this relationship across different market capitalizations—large, medium, and small-cap—by categorizing data from each country. This methodological approach distinguishes the study from previous research (Iwasaki & Mizobata, 2020; Jain & Kalyani, 2023; Maniruzzaman, Hossain, & Sayaduzzaman, 2024; Nashier & Gupta, 2023) and offers a nuanced understanding of ownership incentives.

Utilizing a random sample of 365 firms from Thomson Reuters data between 2005 and 2019, the study applies panel data models to control for unobserved heterogeneity and uses instrumental variable techniques to address endogeneity concerns. This detailed stratification based on market capitalization is essential for understanding the varying incentives and approaches among owners at different scales.

The article offers valuable insights into the impact of ownership concentration on firm performance in emerging markets, emphasizing the importance of tailored corporate governance and financial management practices. It provides empirical evidence supporting a positive correlation between ownership concentration and firm performance, demonstrating methodological rigor and enhancing the validity of its findings. The research also identifies areas for future exploration, including causality and temporal dynamics in the relationship between ownership and performance, contributing significantly to both academic research and practical corporate governance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

For more than two decades, academics have been studying the impact of ownership concentration and control on organizational performance. The possibility of a clash between

a company's managers and owners can be traced back to the extensive investigation of (Berle & Means, 1932). Shareholders with a large number of shares have been increasingly scrutinized by managers to ensure that they use their ownership rights to work in the best interests of the investors. Managers are observed by institutional investors more than individual members of the board of directors, as they don't have any investment in the firm (Shleifer & Vishny, 1986).

The aim was to enhance firm performance through ownership concentration for improved monitoring and through managerial equity holdings to boost managerial dedication while reducing excessive perks. Empirical studies largely concentrated on exploring the link between managerial ownership and the overall value of the firm. Following (Stulz, 1988) who predicted a concave relationship, several papers, including (Hermalin & Weisbach, 1991; Holderness, Kroszner, & Sheehan, 1999; McConnell & Servaes, 1990; Morck, Shleifer, & Vishny, 1988) discovered that while business value declines at greater management ownership levels, it increases at lower ones.

It was believed that the findings of these single-equation experiments demonstrated management entrenchment over a certain level of insider ownership. Since the 1990s, extensive global study of ownership patterns has revealed that a high degree of ownership concentration is prevalent and scattered shareholdings are far less common than expected (Becht & Röell, 1999; La Porta, Lopez-de-Silanes, & Shleifer, 1999). As a result, the main concern shifted to the possibility of the majority shareholders expropriating the minority investors (Faccio & Lang, 2002; Gugler & Weigand, 2003; Lehmann & Weigand, 2000). Significant shareholders can incur costs by pursuing objectives divergent from smaller shareholders, potentially exploiting or disadvantaging the latter. Concentrated ownership eases investments in R&D and entrepreneurship while deterring takeover threats, benefiting long-term investment. Researchers like (Baysinger, Kosnik, & Turk, 1991; Hill & Snell, 1988; Lacetera, 2001) found positive relationship between ownership concentration and R&D.

Numerous studies suggest a positive (or positive but diminishing) relationship, often curvilinear, between management ownership and firm performance, supporting interest alignment and entrenchment theories. We hypothesize that firms with greater ownership concentration are better monitored, reducing

agency problems between managers and shareholders and thereby positively impacting firm performance.

H₁: There is positive relationship between ownership concentration and firm's performance

This study examines how ownership concentration affects the performance of firms across different market capitalizations in emerging economies, filling a gap in research focused solely on overall firm performance. (Kim & Burnie, 2002) suggest that business cycle fluctuations may influence the time-varying characteristics of the company size effect. On the other hand (Switzer & Tang, 2009) observe that despite potential challenges from leverage, small-cap firms, being hubs of entrepreneurship and innovation, may experience fewer governance issues than larger counterparts, thus potentially explaining their superior performance.

Moreover, (Ganguli & Agrawal, 2009) found a statistically significant positive correlation exists between holding concentration and firm performance among listed mid-cap Indian corporations. Previous research suggests that strategies effective for small-cap companies may not apply to medium or large-cap firms, as the latter typically exhibit strong profitability and robust cash flows (La Porta, Lopez-de-Silanes, Shleifer, & Vishny, 2002; Stierwald, 2009). Thus, the final hypotheses of the study are as follows:

H₂: Other things hold constant under the currently prevailing economic conditions: "The firms with high ownership concentration in large-cap firms have high performance".

H₃: Other things hold constant under the currently prevailing economic conditions: "The firms with high ownership concentration in medium cap firms have high performance".

H₄: Other things hold constant under the

currently prevailing economic conditions: "The firms with high ownership concentration in small-cap firms have high performance".

3. METHODOLOGY

Sample and Sources of Data

The study utilizes a sample of 365 firms from 10 emerging economies, chosen based on factors such as market capitalization, economic stability, and regional diversity. This selection aligns with recommendations from Duval and Furceri (2019) and Pazarbasioglu and Mora (2020), who emphasize that emerging markets, despite past crises, have demonstrated resilience and strong medium-term growth potential. To harness this potential, a collective global effort is necessary, with emerging economies learning from each other and major advanced economies fostering multilateral cooperation on free trade, vaccine distribution, financial stability, and climate change. Global development and financial institutions, particularly the IMF, must also collaborate by offering policy advice, financial support, and facilitating cross-country knowledge sharing.

The chosen sample represents a broad geographic and economic spectrum, covering firms from America, Asia, and Africa. These firms are categorized by market capitalization—large, medium, and small—to examine stock returns across different economic scales. The sample encompasses a variety of industries, resulting in a total of 3,394 observations. Panel data analysis is conducted using a dynamic model to handle unbalanced data, addressing issues such as potential firm delistings due to bankruptcy (Keasey, Martinez, & Pindado, 2015). Data on return on assets (as a measure of profitability), ownership concentration, and other control variables were sourced from Thomson Reuters' data stream, covering the period from 2005 to 2019.

Key Variables

Variables	Measurement	Reference
Dependent variable		
ROA	ROA= Profit After Tax/Total Assets	(Al-Ahdal, Hashim, Almaqtari, & Saudagaran, 2023; Alodat, Salleh, Hashim, & Sulong, 2022; Karaca & Eksi, 2012)
Independent variable		
OWC	Represents the percentage of shares held by insiders and top 5% shareholders	(Al-Matari, Al-Matari, & Saif, 2017)
Control variables		
LEV	Total debt / total assets	(Al-Ahdal et al., 2023)
LIQ	Current Ratio	(Al-Ahdal et al., 2023; Nashier & Gupta, 2023)
Size	Natural logarithm of assets	(Nashier & Gupta, 2023)

Additionally, to find the scale subgroups of small, medium, and large-cap firms proposed by (Ronnie Lo, 2009) is followed. A company is categorized as significant ($L_{cap_{it}}$) if its market capitalization is greater than \$8 billion. Similarly, it is classified as a medium cap ($M_{cap_{it}}$) if its market capitalization is between \$1 billion and \$8 billion. A company is a small cap ($S_{cap_{it}}$) if its market capitalization is less than \$1 billion (Younas, Klein, & Zwergel, 2017).

Model Specification

We employ panel data models and the two step GMM to determine the connection between ownership concentration and firm performance in emerging economies. Each estimation

$$(ROA_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1(OWC_{it}) + \beta_2(LEV_{it}) + \beta_3(SIZ_{it}) + \beta_4(LIQ_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{1}$$

$$(L_{cap}ROA_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1(L_{cap}OWC_{it}) + \beta_2(L_{cap}LEV_{it}) + \beta_3(L_{cap}SIZ_{it}) + \beta_4(L_{cap}LIQ_{it}) + L_{cap}\varepsilon_{it} \tag{2}$$

$$(M_{cap}ROA_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1(M_{cap}OWC_{it}) + \beta_2(M_{cap}LEV_{it}) + \beta_3(M_{cap}SIZ_{it}) + \beta_4(M_{cap}LIQ_{it}) + M_{cap}\varepsilon_{it} \tag{3}$$

$$(S_{cap}ROA_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1(S_{cap}OWC_{it}) + \beta_2(S_{cap}LEV_{it}) + \beta_3(S_{cap}SIZ_{it}) + \beta_4(S_{cap}LIQ_{it}) + S_{cap}\varepsilon_{it} \tag{4}$$

The initial findings are predicated upon Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) models. Nonetheless, it is pertinent to note that in the context of simple OLS, estimations exhibit an upward bias. This phenomenon can be attributed to the presence of omitted variable bias, whereby relevant variables are excluded from the model,

technique addresses different econometric issues. Wooldridge (2005) reported that time series variations that cannot be observed in cross-sectional data are studied using panel data models. They support the study of temporal, individual, and group impacts. These models account for the unobserved heterogeneity that is common in panel data. Moreover, Bascle (2008) documented that the IV approach manages the endogeneity bias brought on by endogenous ownership factors. Due to endogeneity, ordinary least squares (OLS) methods yield unreliable results. In the presence of serial autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity, generalized method of moments (GMM) offers accurate parameter estimates.

as well as the oversight of unobserved firm heterogeneity, which engenders a short panel bias in dynamic datasets (Flannery & Hankins, 2013). The study examines the impact of ownership concentration on stock returns of firms in selected developed economies from 2004 to 2018.

$$Return_{nonassets_{it}} = \alpha + \beta_1 Ownership\ concentration_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{5}$$

$$\varepsilon_{i,t} = V_i + u_{i,t},$$

In equation (14) expected returns represent the dependent variable of firm I at time t with $I = 1, 2, \dots, N$; $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, α is a constant term. Ownership concentration is an explanatory variable, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the disturbance with V_i the unobserved firm-specific effect and $u_{i,t}$ the idiosyncratic error. This is a one-

way error component regression model, where $V_{it} \sim IIN(0, \sigma^2 v)$ and independent $u_{it} \sim IIN(0, \sigma^2 u)$ (Abbas & Ali, 2022).

Furthermore, the research adds control variables that include firm-specific factors as well as other macroeconomic indicators. Hence, the overall formulation of the model equation (5) can be expressed as:

$$Return\ on\ assets_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 Ownership\ concentration_{it} + \phi_1 control\ variables_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{6}$$

Control variables consisting of firm-specific factors (leverage, liquidity, size). The research employs a dynamic specification of the model by incorporating a lagged dependent variable as one of the independent variables in order

to address issues related to autocorrelation in residuals, heteroscedasticity, and endogeneity. The equation (6) can be enhanced by include the lagged firms' profitability.

$$Return\ on\ assets_{it} = \alpha + \delta Return\ on\ assets_{it-1} + \beta_1 Ownership\ concentration_{it} + \phi_1 control\ variables_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{7}$$

4. ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

This study presents descriptive statistics for a sample of 3494 observations on various financial variables. Capitalization averages \$10.038 billion with a notable standard deviation of \$24.747 billion, ranging from \$1 billion to \$370 billion. Ownership concentration (OWC) averages

24.877, varying from 0.06 to 90.56. Return on Assets (ROA) averages 54.907 with a range from 0.54 to 100. Leverage (LEV) averages 57.04 with a range from 0.01 to 89.99. Liquidity (LIQ) averages 45.124, ranging from 19.51 to 97.36. Size averages 11.552 with a range from 1.239 to 21.896. These statistics provide insights into the distribution and variability of financial metrics within the sample, crucial for financial analysis and decision-making.

Panel A

Descriptive statistics: Full sample

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Cap in \$b	3494	10.038	24.747	1	370
OWC	3494	24.877	8.027	.06	90.56
ROA	3494	54.907	9.082	.54	100
LEV	3494	57.04	15.106	.01	89.99
LIQ	3494	45.124	4.325	19.51	97.36
Size	3320	11.552	2.636	1.239	21.896

Panel A shows the summary statistics for proxies used in our empirical model, including mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values.

The dataset of 946 observations on large capitalization (Cap) firms reveals a mean Cap of \$29.262 billion, indicating significant market presence in panel B. Ownership concentration (OWC) averages at 24.412, suggesting efficient operational management. Return on Assets (ROA) stands at 54.615%, showcasing profitability. Large cap firms exhibit a mean Leverage (LEV)

of 57.066, implying strategic debt utilization. Liquidity (LIQ) averages at 44.387, ensuring short-term obligation coverage. The firms' Size, with a mean of 12.307, highlights their considerable scale. This concise analysis offers valuable insights into the financial dynamics of large cap firms.

Panel B

Descriptive Statistics: Large cap

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Cap in \$b	946	29.262	41.759	1	370
OWC	946	24.412	9.746	.06	90.55
ROA	946	54.615	9.717	.54	99.81
LEV	946	57.066	16.27	5.23	89.98
LIQ	946	44.387	5.256	19.51	83.41
Size	899	12.307	2.581	1.239	19.464

Panel B shows the summary statistics for proxies used in our empirical model, including mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values for large-cap firms.

Panel C

Descriptive Statistics: Med Cap

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Cap in \$b	1158	6.275	18.701	3	370
OWC	1158	24.654	8.754	.07	90.56
ROA	1158	55.445	10.145	18.94	100
LEV	1158	56.567	16.632	1.6	89.99
LIQ	1158	45.596	4.833	20.63	97.36
Size	1091	11.586	2.591	2.323	21.896

Panel C shows the summary statistics for proxies used in our empirical model, including mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values of medium-cap firms.

Panel C presents descriptive statistics for financial variables of Med Cap with 1158 observations. Mean capitalization is \$6.275B with a significant standard deviation of \$18.701B. Ownership concentration (OWC) averages 24.654 with a deviation of 8.754. Return on assets (ROA) shows a mean of 55.445% with a deviation of 10.145%. The mean leverage ratio (LEV) is 56.567 with a deviation of 16.632. Liquidity (LIQ) stands at 45.596 on average with a deviation of 4.833. Size, based on log of total assets, has a mean of 11.586 with a deviation of 2.591, though data is available for only 1091 entities. The findings highlight significant variability across financial metrics, offering insights for strategic decision-

making within Med Cap’s financial landscape.

The table displays key descriptive statistics for small-cap firms. Market capitalization averages \$2.76 billion with notable variability. The mean value of Ownership concentration (OWC) is 25.25, indicating moderate liquidity differences. Return on Assets (ROA) is 54.696 with relatively consistent performance. Leverage (LEV) is 57.175, showing varied debt structures. Liquidity (LIQ) is relatively homogeneous at 45.214. However, missing data for the “Size” variable limits analysis. These insights provide a concise overview of small-cap characteristics, guiding further financial exploration.

Panel D

Descriptive Statistics: Small Cap

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Cap in \$b	1655	2.763	10.9	1	339
OWC	1655	25.254	5.387	.34	90.55
ROA	1655	54.696	7.032	.55	99.7
LEV	1655	57.175	12.384	.01	89.99
LIQ	1655	45.214	2.807	31.18	77.07
Size	1585	11.054	2.481	2.438	20.715

Panel D shows the summary statistics for proxies used in our empirical model, including mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values for small-cap firms.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation coefficients for dependent and independent variables are shown in the table. Correlation coefficients range from -0.002 for total assets and expected returns to 0.43 for

ownership concentration and ROA. The results show that the variables included in the study are weakly correlated, suggesting that multi-co-linearity is not a concern in the regression analysis.

Panel E

Pairwise correlation matrix for the entire sample

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) Cap in \$b	1.000					
(2) OWC	-0.111*	1.000				
	(0.000)					
(3) ROA	0.034*	0.004	1.000			
	(0.043)	(0.823)				
(4) LEV	0.058*	0.025	0.207*	1.000		
	(0.001)	(0.137)	(0.000)			
(5) LIQ	-0.140*	0.079*	0.173*	0.171*	1.000	
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)		
(6) Size	0.172*	-0.016	-0.048*	0.036*	-0.055*	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.350)	(0.006)	(0.039)	(0.002)	

Panel E shows the relationship between the explanatory variables in the empirical model for the whole sample, where * means that the relationship is significant at p0.05.

Panel F

Pairwise correlation matrix for large-cap firms

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) Cap in \$b	1.000					
(2) OWC	-0.169*	1.000				
	(0.000)					
(3) ROA	0.083*	-0.066*	1.000			
	(0.011)	(0.042)				
(4) LEV	0.117*	-0.021	0.199*	1.000		
	(0.000)	(0.515)	(0.000)			
(5) LIQ	-0.170*	0.196*	0.165*	0.144*	1.000	
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.000)		
(6) Size	0.182*	-0.071*	-0.064	0.016	-0.091*	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.034)	(0.055)	(0.629)	(0.006)	

Panel F shows the relationship between the explanatory variables in the empirical model for the large-cap firms' sample, where * means that the relationship is significant at p0.05.

Panel G

Pairwise correlation matrix for medium-cap firms

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) Cap in \$b	1.000					
(2) OWC	-0.094*	1.000				
	(0.001)					
(3) ROA	0.034	-0.021	1.000			
	(0.251)	(0.476)				
(4) LEV	0.057	0.036	0.304*	1.000		
	(0.051)	(0.222)	(0.000)			
(5) LIQ	-0.068*	-0.017	0.245*	0.153*	1.000	
	(0.021)	(0.569)	(0.000)	(0.000)		
(6) Size	0.092*	0.014	-0.091*	0.045	-0.075*	1.000
	(0.002)	(0.633)	(0.003)	(0.138)	(0.013)	

Panel-G shows the relationship between the explanatory variables in the empirical model for the medium cap firms' sample, where * means that the relationship is significant at p0.05.

Panel H

Pairwise correlation matrix for small-cap firms

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) Cap in \$b	1.000					
(2) OWC	-0.007	1.000				
	(0.781)					
(3) ROA	0.009	0.131*	1.000			
	(0.714)	(0.000)				
(4) LEV	-0.011	0.054*	0.098*	1.000		
	(0.658)	(0.029)	(0.000)			
(5) LIQ	-0.022	0.044	0.030	0.239*	1.000	
	(0.372)	(0.071)	(0.226)	(0.000)		
(6) Size	0.050*	0.024	0.022	0.057*	0.058*	1.000
	(0.047)	(0.340)	(0.381)	(0.022)	(0.021)	

Panel H shows the relationship between the explanatory variables in the empirical model for the small-cap firms' sample, where * means that the relationship is significant at p0.05.

Table 1

Results of Pooled OLS and Fixed Effect

	Full sample		Large Cap		Medium Cap		Small Cap	
	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE	POLS	FE
OWC	0.002** (0.019)	0.013 (0.019)	-0.087*** (0.033)	0.76** (0.035)	0.011 (0.038)	0.002 (0.043)	0.1666 (0.000)	0.155 (0.000)
LIQ	0.307*** (0.038)	0.013 (0.019)	0.252*** (0.067)	0.332*** (0.080)	0.537 (0.000)	0.399 (0.000)	-0.068 (0.279)	-0.0316 (0.654)
LEV	0.103*** (0.010)	0.093*** (0.012)	0.252*** (0.067)	0.092*** (0.025)	.115 (0.000)	0.094 (0.000)	0.39 (0.007)	0.533 (0.001)
Size	-.159*** (0.058)	0.145 (0.135)	0.252*** (0.067)	0.092*** (0.025)	-0.33 (0.000)	-0.21 (0.420)	0.464 (0.50)	0.243 (0.012)
Constant	36.996*** (1.908)	33.119*** (2.516)	42.001*** (3.414)	31.634*** (5.878)	25.915*** (3.455)	34.667*** (4.845)	50.78*** (2.934)	46.23** (3.598)
R ²	0.0601	0.045	0.067	0.045	0.15	0.15	0.02	0.19
No of Obs	3,320	3320	899	899	1091	1091	1585	1585

Table 1 shows the results of Pooled OLS and FE for all models. Standard errors appear in parentheses and are robust to heteroscedasticity. ***, ** and * represent a 1%, 5% and 10% significance level using two-tailed test, respectively.

The analysis presented in Table 1, which includes results from Pooled OLS and Fixed Effects (FE) regression models across different market capitalization categories, reveals several key relationships between explanatory variables and firm performance. Notably, ownership concentration (OWC) shows a significant positive impact only within the Small Cap segment, suggesting that it plays a crucial role in enhancing performance for smaller firms. Liquidity (LIQ) maintains a significant positive influence across all market segments, highlighting its importance in firm performance regardless of firm size. Conversely, leverage (LEV) is positively associated with performance in both the Full sample and Large Cap segments, with a pronounced effect observed in Small Cap firms. On the other hand, firm size demonstrates a significant negative relationship with performance in most segments, indicating performance disparities related to firm size.

The constant term remains significant across all segments, reinforcing its importance as a performance determinant. Despite these insights, the overall explanatory power of the models, as indicated by the R-squared values, is relatively low, suggesting that additional factors might be influencing firm performance that are not captured in the models. These results underscore the complexity of performance drivers across different market capitalization

categories, pointing to the necessity of tailored strategies to enhance performance based on firm size.

Final Results: Overall Sample and Subgroups

The final analysis offers several significant insights. First, the coefficient for the lagged dependent variable, which reflects the persistence of profitability, is consistently positive and statistically significant across all model specifications (Column 1: $\beta = 0.530$, $t = 9.298$; Column 2: $\beta = 0.767$, $t = 5.391$; Column 3: $\beta = 0.323$, $t = 2.634$; Column 4: $\beta = 0.723$, $t = 5.069$). This indicates a strong autocorrelation in profitability, suggesting that previous profitability levels have a considerable effect on current profitability. Second, while ownership concentration's impact on profitability is positive, it is relatively modest. The coefficient estimates for ownership concentration are positive across all models, with statistical significance at the 10% level in Columns 1 and 2, and at the 5% level in Column 3. These results are consistent with findings from Ganguli and Agrawal (2009) and Nashier and Gupta (2023), but differ from those of Abdullah et al. (2019) in emerging economies. In Column 4, however, the coefficient for ownership concentration loses statistical significance, suggesting a weaker relationship between ownership concentration and profitability in smaller-cap firms.

Table 2

A Two-Step System GMM Methods for Ownership Concentration and Firm's performance in Emerging Economies: (Overall sample, LCP, MCAP & SCAP)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
VARIABLES	Profitability	Profitability	Profitability	Profitability
Lag dependent	0.530*** (0.057)	0.767*** (0.142)	0.323*** (0.123)	0.723*** (0.143)
Ownership Concentration	0.013* (0.005)	0.009* (0.006)	0.011* (0.007)	0.005 (0.003)
Liquidity	0.064*** (0.024)	0.017 (0.032)	0.139** (0.057)	0.139** (0.057)
Leverage	0.041*** (0.010)	0.016 (0.016)	0.036 (0.028)	0.036 (0.028)
Firm size	-0.042 (0.079)	-0.038 (0.089)	0.023 (0.213)	0.023 (0.213)
Constant	6.732*** (2.034)	-1.477 (4.993)	6.424 (6.660)	6.424 (6.660)
Observations	4580	2234	2476	1476
Number of Id	509	406	303	103
AR(2)	0.449	0.294	0.844	0.444
Hansen	0.099	0.067	0.038	0.071

Table 2. Shows the results for two-step system GMM methods. The dependent variable includes profitability. Explanatory variables include majority shareholders, firm size, leverage, profitability and corporate governance. ***, **, * indicate the level of significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

5. CONCLUSION

The study provides an in-depth examination of how ownership concentration affects firm performance across emerging economies, focusing on different market capitalization categories. By analyzing a dataset of 365 companies from 10 emerging countries over a 15-year period, this research offers valuable insights into corporate governance. The results validate the anticipated positive link between ownership concentration and firm performance, indicating that greater ownership concentration enhances firm oversight, reduces agency conflicts, and improves profitability. This supports Shleifer and Vishny's (1997) view that concentrated ownership is pivotal for effective corporate governance. The findings align with previous research by Claessens and Djankov (1999), Leech and Leahy (1991), and Ganguli and Agrawal (2009), which highlights that concentrated ownership lowers agency costs through active monitoring by major shareholders, thereby boosting firm performance.

Moreover, the analysis reveals that liquidity significantly affects profitability, especially in smaller firms. This underscores the importance of designing corporate governance and financial management strategies that cater to the specific needs of firms based on their market

capitalization. The study also emphasizes that past performance has a lasting impact on current financial results, showcasing the persistence effect in profitability. This research enriches our understanding of ownership structures and suggests future research directions, such as investigating causal relationships and the temporal aspects of ownership-performance dynamics.

Competing Interests

The author did not declare any competing interest.

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